

Methodologies of business process reengineering model for e-government

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Abstract

The development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has made many electronic services possible. Electronic government is a system of organizational, legal measures and technical tools aimed at ensuring the provision of public services to individuals and legal entities, as well as interdepartmental electronic cooperation.

There are many approaches to BPR (e.g. Hammer, Davenport, and Short, 2018), but no matter which one you follow, a BPR initiative is a risky venture and several factors must be considered in order to be successful. Another important factor is aligning the transformation efforts with the organization's strategic direction, demonstrated in terms of financial performance, customer service, employee value, and the organization's vision. In the paper, implementation analysis of several BPR methodologies is provided. According to the results of the research, the characteristics of the chosen direction should take into account while implementing BPR methods in the digitization of electronic government.

1. Introduction

Nowadays organizations, in order to successfully withstand these challenging operating conditions, must rethink their key strategies aimed at minimizing the cost of services and products, as well as improving customer satisfaction, service quality. One of the goals of e-government is to reduce redundancies, avoid bureaucracy and prevent corruption. There has been an evolution from function-oriented organizations, which organized around functions to process-oriented ones, which organized around processes (Moon M. J. 2002). E-

government processes can be implemented through business models. Thinking in terms of consequent steps, Business Process Reengineering (BPR) is becoming increasingly important as a means of improving process efficiency and competitiveness (Grabow B. and Christine S., 2002). BPR models is a management practice that radically rethinks the associated tasks needed to achieve a particular business outcome. The main purpose of BPR is to analyse workflows within and between business functions in order to optimize the end-to-end business process and eliminate tasks that do not improve performance or provide value to the customer.

In addition, it is very important to choose the right methodology that meets the needs of the project, is understandable and supported by the project team. The BPR methodology provides a framework for implementing BPR efforts (Caren L., Jungwoo L., 2001). It is used to support reengineering-related activities such as defining project boundaries, selecting the right people for the BPR team, identifying the project manager, selecting, identifying and analysing business processes that are candidates for reengineering (Heeks R. 2003). There are a large number of BPR methodologies, though which model to choose for e-government depends on the information system that provides the service (David C. and Donald F. N, 2008). This paper presents a report on a study that developed a BPR models with reengineering for the implementation of local e-government by comparing other BPR methodology steps.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. E-Government Models

The majority of BPR methodologies share common features and steps. After the Japanese wave of business process management, the concept of business process reengineering emerged and shook the BPM world (Deloitte and Touche, 2001). In the following sections are described a representative the features of some BPR models, which are widely used in the organization of electronic government in developed countries, are discussed. In the end, we describe the differences of these methodologies and the value and

the importance of each special step in a BPR effort. Moreover, various recommendations and opinions are presented on the effectiveness and using areas of application of these models. Finally, there is a discussion how BPR seems to be applied in the future. In general, BPR involves the analysis and transformation of several major components of a business. These include: strategy, organization, process, technology, culture (Bwalka K.J., and Healy, M. 2010).

2.1.1. Manganelli and Klein Methodology

According to Manganelli and Klein the goal of the reengineering project lies in dramatic increase of competitiveness and the tool for its achievement is implementation of new IT. This method, a business should focus its rethinking processes and initiatives only on the most important areas that affect the company's strategic and tactical goals and customer requirements (Gigova T.B. and Geshanova N.S., 2020). It includes following steps: i) Determine the purpose of the business reengineering project, ii) Select the main processes for reengineering, iii) Determine what you want to achieve from future process reengineering metrics, iv) Develop a technology design and a new workspace structure that will support the rebuilt flows and process maps, v) Implement BPR results throughout the organization.

2.1.2. Davenport's and Short's methodology

Davenport and Short position IT at the heart of BPR. They recognize the existence of a recursive relationship between IT capabilities and BPR, meaning that IT should be considered in terms of how it supports new or redesigned business processes, and recursively business processes and process improvement should be considered in terms of the capabilities IT can provide (Cambridge University Press, 2005). Believing that BPR should be integrated with approaches like Continuous Process Improvement (CPI) (Ashish D., 2022), Davenport and Short suggest that the redesign effort of an organization involves five major steps. They are: i) Develop Business Vision and Process Objectives,

ii) Identify Processes to Be Redesigned, iii) Understand and Measure Existing Processes, iv) Identify IT levers, v) Design and Build a Prototype of the Process.

2.1.3. *The Hammer / Champy methodology*

The principles Hammer and Champy methodology should consider to organize around outcomes, not tasks. Moreover, having those who use the output of the process perform the process and subsume information-processing work into the real work that produces the information. There exist link parallel activities instead of integrating their results. Consequently, it leads to put the decision point where the work is performed, and build control into the process. In this methodology is also included capture information once and at the source (Lehberger K., 2000). In fact, a BPR effort changes practically everything in the organisation: people, jobs, managers and values, because these aspects are linked together (Layne K., and Lee J. 2001). The six phases of the methodology are next presented: i) Introduction into Business Reengineering, ii) Identification of Business Processes, iii) Selection of Business Processes, iv) Understanding of Selected Business Processes, v) Redesign of the Selected Business Processes, vi) Implementation of Redesigned Business Processes.

2.1.4. *Object-oriented BPR*

Today object-oriented technology is widely and successfully used for the development of software systems. Currently many attempts are being made to use object-oriented technology for modelling organizations and their processes. A good argument for using object orientation to model organizations is that it models the company in a way that is very close to reality promoting in this way comprehensibility and understanding (Abdelmajid O.M., 2008). The object's behavior and information can be used by other objects. Work tasks in an organization can be modeled as object. Steps are as followed: i) OO BPR is to ask fundamental questions about the organization, and not take anything for granted, ii) OO BPR is to reinvent the business processes, iii) Implementing the new business process, using the *Domain Model* and Business Process Maps (Geert Poels, 2019).

2.1.5. Methodology analysis

Most BPR methodologies share common phases and features. The four popular BPR methodologies described above are the Manganeli and Klein Methodology, the Davenport methodology, Hammer/Chempy methodology, the Process Analysis and Design Method (PADM) and a representative set of methodologies that share phases and features, but also differ in their approach to reengineering. Their main differences are as follows: i) whether they recommend detailed modelling and analysis of the current situation or not, ii) whether they support incremental or radical changes to business processes, iii) whether they offer to study successful organizations before starting a BPR project.

The purpose of each phase, its value and potential risks that it carries, as well as the known techniques used to complete each phase, are described. Each of the above methodologies is then placed within the scope of this comparison and some of the findings are discussed (Janseen M. and Wargenar R. 2004).

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Results

Measurable properties and goals for each process, like cost, quality, life cycle, lead time and customer satisfaction, as well as technology to support the processes are defined. A set of future scenarios are given in an effort to predict the effect of changes. A list of risks critical success factors is also given. An integrated, intelligence-based foundation for the conception, representation, development, and implementation of distinctive workplace processes that are responsive to a company's need to effectively meet the needs of its customers can be formed by the power of Business Process Reengineering (BPR) and Object Oriented Analysis (OOA).

According to the analysis of BPR methods, it can be said that, taking into account that each method has its own characteristics, it is important to choose the field that is suitable for its application. The main differences among the BPR methodologies are

approach of the business process and common steps are redesigning the process according to the individual factors of the particular sphere of electron government.

3.2. Applying BPR for E-government in Uzbekistan

The reengineering object model is implemented in Uzbekistan by integrating all authority organizations and ministry departments, agencies (E-Government, 2020). As a result of the reengineering researches, the activities of state and ministries-departments, their structural and regional units will be modernized on the basis of innovative methods based on Processes and Communications (BPR) using innovative management methods.

Fig 1. State and economic management bodies criteria for assessing the complexity of administrative processes

Implementation of ICT in public administration consists of several stages.

The first stage - the creation of web portals is characterized by the government's entry into the electronic network structure. At this stage, the government has one or more websites that serve as information providers (Sa'dullayev M., 2015).

The second stage - with the participation of the web portal, it is possible to provide users with a lot of special and new information through government websites. This

information may consist of government publications, legal documents, and new information.

The third stage - interactive web portals, along with providing services to the population, also increase the consistency of relations between state structures and citizens. National government websites connect the user directly to ministries, departments and agencies in the form of a web portal.

The fourth stage - the information flow web portal for the user ensures receiving documents and reaching agreements through the network. Citizens use visas, passports, birth or death certificates, licenses, permits and other information services.

The fifth stage is a fully integrated web portal that provides service and communication through the government portal network, ensuring that the network user receives the optional service on time. Electronic - online use of state services is both time-saving and financially convenient (Y. Marqayev, 2022).

3.3. Statistics.

In recent years, this practice has developed a lot in our country and competitive results are being achieved (Table 1). According to statistics, in June 2022, 636 000 704 public services were provided to individuals and legal entities through the Public Service Centers (PSC). 142,254 of them, or more than 22 percent, were submitted online, that is, through Unified interactive government services (my.gov.uz) .

Table 1. The most public services provided through the PSC in 2022

№	Name of Public Service	Quantity
1	Electronic digital signature	1 145 385
2	Putting the child in line for kindergarten	627 049
3	Issuing a cadastral passport	284 984

4	Allocation of benefits to citizens	246 676
5	Issuance of a new model driver's license	225 554

4. Conclusions.

In order to come to a conclusion on the efficiency of models, it is better to present a methodology comparison framework that includes five major phases of a BPR project: i) Learning process phase, ii) Create a business vision, iii) Modeling and analyzing current processes, iv) Modeling and analyzing to be processes, v) Transition to a continuous process improvement effort (Carbo, T., Williams, J. G., and Emeritus, P. 2005). As a clear example of this, it is enough to pay attention to the numbers reflected in the statistics. This comparison serves as a basis for carrying out targeted inspections and reengineering activities in relevant ministries and agencies. The statistics of the Public Service Centers show that the population is effectively using these services. Accordingly, the establishment of state and economy bodies in Uzbekistan based on the BPR model is showing its effectiveness.

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